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TREBALL FINAL DE MÀSTER

Detection of plastic waste in various water bodies using remote sensing data.

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Resume

This thesis presents a processing pipeline for detecting floating plastic debris in aquatic environments using optical satellite imagery and machine learning. The pipeline combines two complementary models: an instance segmentation model applied to optical features (color, shape, texture) to detect debris-like objects, and a pixel-wise classification model using spectral indices to distinguish plastics from natural materials such as algae, pumice, and timber. Outputs include trained models, evaluation metrics, and a curated dataset for future monitoring and research.

Growing interest in remote sensing for marine litter has led to promising AI-based methods. A key reference is [Biermann 2020], which introduced the Floating Debris Index (FDI) and demonstrated detection of plastics in Sentinel-2 imagery using spectral classification; this study forms the basis of the present work. Other studies applied XGBoost [Duarte 2023] and deep learning segmentation [Rußwurm 2023], emphasizing both model design and the critical role of data quality.

The study relies on Sentinel-2 MSI imagery, particularly its 13 spectral bands useful for debris detection. Data comes in Level-1C and Level-2A formats, with atmospheric correction applied via Sen2Cor (default) or ACOLITE DSF (compared during preprocessing). Spectral indices like NDVI and FDI form input feature space for the classification task. For modeling, the Ultralytics YOLOv11 instance segmentation architecture was used for object detection, and a Support Vector Machine (SVM) was applied for spectral classification. Datasets were created using Roboflow (segmentation), and QGIS (mostly for classification).

Study sites included Visegrad Dam, Durban, Omoa, Accra, Japan, Tonga, and Barbados, chosen from scientific/media reports. Atmospheric correction methods were evaluated, with Sen2Cor selected for better plastic separation. Classification samples were labeled in QGIS, cleaned with Isolation Forest, and balanced. The SVM was trained in an overfitted fashion to reproduce class-specific signatures rather than generalize broadly. Segmentation training data was created from RGB tiles annotated in Roboflow. Three YOLOv11 model sizes (nano, small, medium) were tested in a cascade setup with hyperparameters tuned per configuration. Classification performance was evaluated on both test splits and independent sites, with and without segmentation-based filtering.

The segmentation model (YOLOv11m) achieved moderate performance (validation mAP50–95: 0.214 for boxes, 0.074 for masks), with generalization limited by data scarcity and imagery complexity. The SVM classifier performed strongly on test data (balanced accuracy: 0.972, macro-F1: 0.973), though likely overfitted. Segmentation masks significantly improved classification precision in

cluttered scenes; e.g., F1 increased from 0.281 to 0.827 (Visegrad) and from 0.043 to 0.529 (Omoa). Precision gains were clear in complex cases, while simpler scenes showed minor improvement. Overall, the two-stage approach proved effective but highlighted the need for more training data and robustness to edge cases.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Context of the Problem

Plastic pollution in aquatic environments has become a critical global environmental concern. Large quantities of plastic waste enter rivers, lakes, and oceans every year from sources such as urban runoff, industrial discharge, tourism, and poorly managed landfills. These plastics often accumulate as visible debris such as bottles, packaging, and bags that float on the surface or gather along shorelines. The presence of macroplastics disrupts aquatic ecosystems, poses ingestion and entanglement risks to marine wildlife, and damages natural habitats.

Despite international attention to the problem, global plastic production levels remain high. A key factor is the outsourcing of manufacturing from developed nations to regions with less stringent environmental regulations. In many of these countries, ecological monitoring systems are either underdeveloped or absent, making it difficult to track or mitigate pollution.

As highlighted in the review by [Chen 2024], interest in this area has grown steadily, indicating both the complexity of the problem and the opportunity to address it with modern geospatial technologies.

1.2 Limitations of Traditional Methods

Traditional methods for detecting plastic waste in aquatic environments rely heavily on manual observation and human intervention. These include shoreline and on-water visual inspections, physical sampling, and incident reporting based on sightings by marine vessels, coast guards, or citizen scientists. In many cases, evidence of pollution is only documented when it becomes visible or reported through news channels or local authorities, leading to significant gaps in spatial and temporal coverage.

Drones and aircraft have been used in some cases, but their range is limited, and they require favorable weather and skilled operation. These tools are not practical for routine, large-scale monitoring and remain logistically and economically constrained.

1.3 Opportunity Provided by Remote Sensing

Remote sensing provides a powerful approach for detecting plastic waste in water bodies by leveraging the spectral capabilities of modern Earth observation systems. Many satellites are equipped with multispectral sensors that include bands in the visible, near-infrared, and shortwave infrared ranges useful for distinguishing plastic debris from natural surfaces like water, vegetation, or foam. These systems typically offer revisit times ranging from 2 to 5 days, depending on latitude and sensor configuration, enabling continuous monitoring of dynamic environments. The large spatial coverage allows for systematic surveys across vast and remote regions. Importantly, many satellite constellations provide free and open data access, making large-scale environmental monitoring feasible without high operational costs.

1.4 Motivation

This topic was chosen due to my professional background in working with Earth Observation data and a strong interest in exploring machine learning and AI techniques for remote sensing applications.

1.5 Objectives of the Work

The primary objective of this thesis is to create and evaluate a processing pipeline (technological chain of models) for the detection of floating plastic debris in aquatic environments using optical satellite imagery and machine learning techniques. The proposed approach integrates two complementary components:

1. An object detection and segmentation model applied to optical imagery, used to identify and delineate debris-like structures based on their visual appearance.
2. A supervised classification model based on spectral indices, developed for pixel-level material identification to characterize the composition of detected debris.

This study aims to assess the practical performance, complementarity, and limitations of combining these two modeling strategies in real-world remote sensing scenarios.

To achieve this, the project involves:

- Collecting and labeling training data for both segmentation and classification tasks;
- Developing preprocessing tools for spectral index computation and data preparation;
- Training and tuning the models to optimize performance.

The expected outcomes include trained instance segmentation and classification models, performance evaluation metrics, and a set of annotated datasets for future use.

1.6 Data Science Workflow

This project combines geospatial processing, image analysis, and machine learning for detecting floating debris in satellite imagery. The pipeline begins with YOLO-based instance segmentation on Sentinel-2 true color composites (TCI) to localize debris-like objects. These segmented regions are then passed to a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier, which performs pixel-level classification using spectral indices (NDVI and FDI). As part of the dataset preparation for classification, a comparative evaluation of two atmospheric correction algorithms: Sen2Cor and ACOLITE DSF was conducted to identify the most suitable preprocessing approach for reliable index-based detection.

The geospatial workflow involves handling both raster and vector data to create masks and training labels. The project follows a full data science pipeline: from EO data acquisition and preprocessing to model training, evaluation, and visualization, using tools and libraries such as Rasterio (GDAL), QGIS, Ultralytics, scikit-learn, and pandas.

1.7 Document Structure

The thesis is organized as follows:

- Chapter 2 reviews the current state of the art in plastic detection using remote sensing and machine learning.
- Chapter 3 provides the theoretical background necessary to understand the methodology.
- Chapter 4 presents the methodology, including data collection, preprocessing, and model design.

- Chapter 5 details the methodological contributions of this work.
- Chapter 6 presents the results and discussion.
- Chapter 7 concludes the study and outlines future research directions.

CHAPTER 2

State of the Art

In recent years, research on the detection of plastic pollution in aquatic environments using remote sensing has steadily grown. A comprehensive review by [Chen 2024] summarizes the development of methods and datasets in the field of Marine and Inland Water Plastics Remote Sensing (MIWPRS), highlighting the increasing interest in optical satellite data and the integration of artificial intelligence techniques for large-scale monitoring. However, challenges remain in developing continuous observation systems and robust impact assessment models.

One of the foundational studies for this work is [Biermann 2020], which introduced the Floating Debris Index (FDI) and demonstrated that floating macroplastics are detectable in Sentinel-2 imagery. The study used spectral shape analysis and a Naive Bayes classifier to differentiate plastics from seaweed and other organic materials, achieving promising results across multiple test sites. The nomenclature of classes from this publication served as the foundation for this thesis project.

Machine learning approaches have also been explored, such as in [Duarte 2023], which applied an Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) classifier using Sentinel-2 spectral bands and derived indices to distinguish plastic debris from other floating materials. The study showed high classification accuracy in several scenarios, including one trained on synthetic data, though the authors note challenges with generalization due to sub-pixel debris coverage and mixed spectral responses.

Deep learning methods have also been applied at larger scales. In [Rußwurm 2023], the authors trained a segmentation model based on U-Net and U-Net++ architectures to detect marine debris in Sentinel-2 coastal imagery. They emphasized the importance of data quality and label refinement, finding that model performance was more influenced by dataset construction than model architecture. This supports the growing consensus that data-centric approaches are key to advancing marine debris detection using remote sensing.

CHAPTER 3

Preliminaries

3.1 Sentinel-2 MSI Sensor

The Sentinel-2 satellites, operated by the European Space Agency (ESA), are equipped with the MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI) [Copernicus 2023], which captures imagery in 13 spectral bands ranging from visible to shortwave infrared (443–2190 nm).

MSI Band	Descriptor	S-2A (nm)	S-2B (nm)	Resolution (m)
Band 1	Coastal Aerosol	442.7	442.3	60
Band 2	Blue	492.4	492.1	10
Band 3	Green	559.8	559.0	10
Band 4	Red	664.6	665.0	10
Band 5	Red Edge 1	704.1	703.8	20
Band 6	Red Edge 2	740.5	739.1	20
Band 7	Red Edge 3	782.8	779.7	20
Band 8	NIR	832.8	833.0	10
Band 8a	Narrow NIR	864.7	864.0	20
Band 9	Water Vapour	945.1	943.2	60
Band 10	SWIR Cirrus	1373.5	1376.9	60
Band 11	SWIR1	1613.7	1610.4	20
Band 12	SWIR2	2202.4	2185.7	20

Table 3.1: Sentinel-2 MSI band characteristics. Selected bands for detecting floating debris are highlighted in bold.

The MSI provides data at spatial resolutions of 10 m, 20 m, and 60 m depending on the band, with a revisit time of approximately 5 days at the equator. It is widely used for land and coastal monitoring due to its high radiometric quality and open data policy.

3.2 Sentinel-2 Scene Granule Structure

Each Sentinel-2 scene corresponds to a single granule [NASA HLS Team 2024] (or tile) defined by the Military Grid Reference System (MGRS). Each granule cov-

ers a fixed $100 \text{ km} \times 100 \text{ km}$ area and follows a regular, georeferenced pixel grid. A key feature is that granules from the same MGRS cell across different acquisition dates share identical spatial geometry — each pixel (Fig. 3.1) corresponds to the same ground location over time.

Figure 3.1: Pixel grid alignment of band data in scene granule.

In addition to image data, granules contain auxiliary files such as scene classification maps, cloud and shadow masks, and quality indicators.

3.3 Processing Levels of Sentinel-2 Data

Sentinel-2 imagery is provided at different processing levels:

- **Level-1C (L1C):** Contains Top-Of-Atmosphere (TOA) reflectance. Includes atmospheric effects. L1C is radiometrically calibrated and orthorectified [[Copernicus Open Access Hub 2024a](#)].
- **Level-2A (L2A):** Contains Bottom-Of-Atmosphere (BOA) reflectance. Generated by the Sen2Cor processor using atmospheric correction applied to L1C inputs [[Copernicus Open Access Hub 2024b](#)].

BOA reflectance is critical for quantitative remote sensing applications, including vegetation and floating debris index calculation.

3.4 Atmospheric Correction Algorithms

- **Sen2Cor:** Sen2Cor is the official ESA processor for atmospheric correction of Sentinel-2 Level-1C data. It produces Level-2A products by cor-

recting Top-Of-Atmosphere (TOA) reflectance for atmospheric effects such as aerosols, water vapor, and ozone, using auxiliary data and a radiative transfer model. [Main-Knorn 2017].

- **ACOLITE DSF** is a scene-based atmospheric correction method available within the ACOLITE processor. It estimates atmospheric parameters by fitting a baseline spectrum using dark pixels in shortwave infrared bands and outputs surface reflectance values from Level-1C inputs. [Vanhellemont 2019].

3.5 Floating Debris Index (FDI)

The Floating Debris Index (FDI) is a spectral index designed to enhance the detection of floating materials on water surfaces in Sentinel-2 imagery. It is adapted from the Floating Algae Index (FAI), originally developed for sensors such as MODIS, MERIS, and Landsat. FDI replaces the red band typically used in FAI with the Sentinel-2 Red Edge 2 (RE2) band (740 nm), better suited for detecting non-vegetated floating debris.

FDI is defined as the difference between the observed near-infrared (NIR) reflectance and a baseline NIR reflectance interpolated from neighboring bands:

$$FDI = R_{NIR} - \left(R_{RE2} + (R_{SWIR1} - R_{RE2}) \cdot \frac{\lambda_{NIR} - \lambda_{RE2}}{\lambda_{SWIR1} - \lambda_{RE2}} \cdot 10 \right) \quad (3.1)$$

Where:

- R is surface reflectance,
- λ is central wavelength,
- NIR = Band 8 (842 nm),
- RE2 = Band 6 (740 nm),
- SWIR1 = Band 11 (1610 nm).

This index leverages the spectral contrast in the NIR region to enhance floating targets. The baseline subtraction minimizes sensitivity to atmospheric conditions and observation geometry, making FDI suitable for detecting small sub-pixel aggregations of floating debris, even under hazy or turbid conditions.

3.6 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

NDVI [Sentinel Hub 2025] is a widely used spectral index for identifying photosynthetically active vegetation. It exploits the strong reflectance contrast between the red and near-infrared bands:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{R_{\text{NIR}} - R_{\text{RED}}}{R_{\text{NIR}} + R_{\text{RED}}} \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

- RED = Band 4 (665 nm),
- NIR = Band 8 (842 nm).

Vegetation absorbs strongly in the red band due to chlorophyll and reflects in the NIR, leading to high NDVI values. Water bodies and non-vegetated materials, in contrast, typically yield low or negative NDVI values. This makes NDVI useful for distinguishing algae and vegetation mats from plastics or timber in aquatic debris detection tasks.

3.7 Ultralytics YOLO Instance Segmentation Model

YOLOv11 (You Only Look Once, version 11) is a state-of-the-art, real-time object detection and instance segmentation model developed by Ultralytics [Ultralytics Docs 2025]. It employs a single-stage architecture that includes a CSPDarknet backbone for efficient feature extraction, a PANet module for multi-scale feature aggregation, and dedicated heads for object classification, bounding box regression, and pixel-level segmentation mask prediction.

Figure 3.2: Scheme of YOLO v11 architecture.

The instance segmentation variant of YOLOv11 is pretrained on the COCO dataset [[Ultralytics 2025](#)] (Common Objects in Context), which contains over 200,000 images annotated with bounding boxes and detailed segmentation masks across 80 object categories. This comprehensive training enables the model to learn robust visual features suitable for precise object localization and segmentation.

3.8 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a supervised learning algorithm widely used for classification tasks. It separates data by finding the optimal hyperplane in a high-dimensional feature space. SVM performs well with limited training data and can handle non-linear boundaries using kernel functions. It has been widely applied in remote sensing for pixel-based classification using spectral features [[Mountrakis 2011](#)].

3.9 Roboflow Platform

Roboflow is an online platform [[Roboflow 2025](#)] that supports dataset preparation, annotation, and augmentation for computer vision tasks. It streamlines the process of labeling and exporting datasets in formats compatible with YOLO and other models. Roboflow also provides tools for visualizing and managing training data.

3.10 QGIS

QGIS (Quantum GIS) is an open-source desktop GIS software used for spatial data visualization, editing, and analysis [[QGIS 2025](#)]. It supports a wide range of raster and vector formats and is frequently used in Earth observation workflows for manual labeling, mask creation, and map layout design.

3.11 Copernicus Browser (Open Access Hub)

The Copernicus Open Access Hub is ESA's official portal [[Copernicus Data Space Browser 2025](#)] for downloading Sentinel satellite data. Users can search for and access Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, and Sentinel-5P products. It provides metadata filtering, footprint-based search, and access to Level-1C and Level-2A imagery.

Planning and Methodology

4.1 Study Area Selection and Motivation

The selection of study sites in this project was driven by a combination of literature review, media reports, and expert consultation. Each location was chosen based on known or suspected presence of floating debris visible in Sentinel-2 imagery, as well as the diversity of materials (e.g., plastics, seaweed, timber, pumice) that may be confused in classification models.

4.1.1 Literature-based Sites

Several study sites were selected based on case studies and annotated examples published in the paper [[Biermann 2020](#)]:

- Accra, Ghana – Selected as a representative site for dense algae blooms.
- Tonga – Chosen for samples of floating volcanic pumice, to help distinguish between plastic and inorganic debris.
- Barbados – Contains large aggregations of Sargassum seaweed, useful for evaluating spectral confusion with plastics.

Figure 4.1: Raft of rubble (pumice) captured by Sentinel-2 mission on 21 August 2019, processed by ESA. Licensed under CC BY-SA 3.0 IGO.

Figure 4.2: On 13 April 2023, one of the Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellites imaged a massive mat of seaweed south of Barbados. European Union, Copernicus Sentinel-2 imagery.

4.1.2 Media-Reported Sites

Additional sites were identified through online reports and photographic evidence of plastic pollution:

- Omoa, Honduras – Frequently cited in news [[ABC News 2020](#)] coverage for plastic accumulation along the coastline, often mixed with organic debris like algae or timber.

Figure 4.3: Floating plastic debris (top left part) in Omoa Bay, Honduras. September 18, 2020

4.1.3 Expert-Suggested Sites

- Yoshiro Island, Japan – Recommended by side experts as a region with visible floating timber debris, offering a different spectral class of non-plastic material to train against.

4.1.4 Validation Sites

To test the generalization of the trained models, three scenes were selected solely for evaluation purposes. These locations were not included in the training phase and represent varied environmental and geographic contexts.

- Visegrad Dam, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Identified from the study [Cerra 2025] and supported by local media reports. Known for significant plastic accumulation [News4Jax 2021].
- Okinawa, Japan
Referenced in [Duarte 2023]. In this study, the site was used to detect floating pumice formations.
- Durban, South Africa
Cited in [Biermann 2020] as a region of plastic pollution based on social media and news sources [Daily Mail 2024].

Figure 4.4: Debris Floating Near Višegrad Hydroelectric Power Plant, 01.03.2021, PlanetScope imagery © 2021 Planet Labs PBC. Used with permission.

In addition to the classification dataset (Table 4.1), a segmentation dataset consisting of 33 Sentinel-2 scenes was prepared to support pixel-wise debris

Region	Scene Identifier	Samples	Purpose
Japan	S2B_MSIL2A_20180713T014649_N0500_R017_T53SKT	timber	training
Omoa	S2B_MSIL2A_20191024T161239_N0500_R140_T16PCC S2A_MSIL2A_20220406T160831_N0400_R140_T16PCC S2B_MSIL2A_20200918T160839_N0500_R140_T16PCC S2A_MSIL2A_20200923T161011_N0500_R140_T16PCC S2B_MSIL2A_20200908T160829_N0500_R140_T16PCC S2B_MSIL2A_20180919T160929_N0500_R140_T16PCC	algae, plastic, water	training
Tongo	S2B_MSIL2A_20190821T215919_N0500_R086_T01KFV	pumice	training
Accra	S2B_MSIL2A_20181031T101139_N0500_R022_T30NYM	algae	training
Barbados	S2B_MSIL2A_20230413T143729_N0509_R096_T21PTP	seaweed	training
Durban	S2B_MSIL2A_20190424T073619_N0500_R092_T36JUM	plastic	validation
Okinawa	S2A_MSIL2A_20211026T020801_N0500_R103_T52RCP	pumice	validation
Visegrad	S2A_MSIL2A_20210325T094031_N0500_R036_T34TCP	plastic, timber	validation

Table 4.1: Summary of Sentinel-2 scenes used for training and validation

detection. The segmentation dataset (Table 1) acts as a superset for the classification dataset, meaning that all scenes used for training the classification model (except Barbados scene) are included within the larger set of scenes prepared for segmentation. Moreover, the segmentation dataset preserves the same geographic distribution of scenes across the study regions – Omoa are prevalent there.

4.2 Data Acquisition

Sentinel-2 scenes were selected and downloaded using the Copernicus Browser, which provides access to archived products and filtering tools for cloud cover, sensing dates, and spatial footprints.

The main selection criteria were:

- Cloud cover below 40%
- Visible shoreline or coastal water regions, where floating debris is likely to accumulate

To facilitate a comparative evaluation of atmospheric correction outputs during exploratory data analysis, two types of products for each scene were downloaded:

- Level-2A (L2A): Surface reflectance products that have already been atmospherically corrected using the Sen2Cor algorithm. These were directly downloaded from the Copernicus Hub and used as-is.
- Level-1C (L1C): Top-of-atmosphere reflectance products, which were processed manually using the ACOLITE DSF algorithm to generate an alternative set of surface reflectance data.

4.3 Overview of Approaches

This study applies two complementary strategies for detecting floating debris in aquatic environments:

1. Object-based segmentation approach applied to RGB imagery, and
2. Spectral classification approach based on pixel-level reflectance indices

Figure 4.5: General scheme of detection and classification pipeline.

The classification pipeline involves spectral feature engineering and a supervised learning model (SVM), while the segmentation task is addressed using an instance segmentation model based on YOLOv11 (Fig. 4.5). The following subsections describe the methodology for each.

4.3.1 Image-Based Instance Segmentation

To detect and localize floating debris in optical satellite imagery, an instance segmentation model based on the YOLOv11 architecture was employed.

The model operates on Sentinel-2 True Color Images (TCI) 8-bit RGB composites derived from surface reflectance data. These images were tiled into smaller patches and manually annotated on the Roboflow platform. Each tile was labeled with instance masks corresponding to a single class: debris, the aim is to detect any visible floating material on the water surface, regardless of its composition.

The model outputs pixel-level instance masks and bounding boxes for each detected object. These debris masks are subsequently used as a filtering mechanism to constrain further analysis to relevant regions: they define spatial areas from which pixels will be extracted for supervised spectral classification using the SVM model.

4.3.2 Supervised Pixel Classification

A Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier was used to assign class labels to individual pixels based on their spectral characteristics. The input feature space consisted of the Floating Debris Index (FDI) and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), both derived from atmospherically corrected Sentinel-2 reflectance data.

This approach is well suited for structured datasets with limited input features and is commonly used in remote sensing for pixel-based classification tasks [Foody 2004].

Training samples were manually selected to represent key material classes such as floating plastic, algae, seaweed, pumice, timber, and background water. To maximize discriminative power within this limited feature space, the classifier was designed to reproduce class-wise spectral signatures observed in the labeled training samples, rather than generalize across the full spectral variability of unseen data.

This overfitting-based design aligns with the overall pipeline structure, where pixel classification is applied only to candidate regions predicted (filtered) by the segmentation model. As such, the classifier is not expected to operate over entire scenes, but rather within a subset of pixels likely to contain debris. This reduces the need for exhaustive dataset annotation and enables controlled classification behavior within known value ranges.

4.3.2.1 Spectral Index Computation

To support the classification of floating debris, two spectral indices: FDI (Floating Debris Index) and NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) were used as primary features. These indices provide a simplified yet informative representation of multispectral Sentinel-2 data by capturing complementary spectral behaviors of natural and artificial floating materials (Fig. 4.6).

Figure 4.6: Spectral signatures for different materials, adapted from [Biermann 2020]

This two-dimensional feature space was first proposed in [Biermann 2020], where it proved effective for differentiating various debris types using supervised learning. Their study (Fig. 4.7) demonstrated that while FDI is most effective at distinguishing water from other materials, it shows limited ability to separate between different debris types. FDI values tend to increase with the amount of material filling a pixel: dense aggregations like seaweed, timber, and foam exhibit high FDI values, while plastics and pumice, which often occupy subpixel areas, fall in a mid-range overlapping zone. Water consistently yields near-zero FDI, making it the most separable class in this dimension.

In contrast, NDVI provides much stronger separation between debris types, particularly due to differences in vegetation content. Seaweed and timber show high NDVI values, plastic debris tends to occupy a low-to-mid NDVI range, and foam and pumice display negative NDVI values, similar to water. This index therefore plays a critical role in differentiating vegetative and non-vegetative materials.

When plotted jointly, NDVI and FDI values result in distinct material clusters in 2D feature space. As shown in [Biermann 2020], materials such as wa-

Figure 4.7: Distribution and class separability in NDVI - FDI feature space, adapted from [Biermann 2020]

ter, foam, plastic, seaweed, timber, and pumice tend to occupy unique zones, enabling a classifier to learn meaningful decision boundaries. These properties motivated the use of NDVI and FDI as the primary features for the Support Vector Machine classifier used in this study.

The classification pipeline leverages this feature space to maximize material discriminability while keeping the input dimensionality low, which helps maintain model interpretability. This decision is further supported by empirical evidence from the literature as well as early visualizations conducted during this study.

4.3.2.2 Atmosphere Correction Methods Comparison

To ensure optimal input quality for spectral index-based classification, two atmospheric correction methods were compared during exploratory data analysis:

- **Sen2Cor**-processed Level-2A scenes, providing ready-to-use surface reflectance;
- **ACOLITE**-processed Level-1C scenes, corrected locally using the Dark Spectrum Fitting (DSF) method.

For each correction method, NDVI and FDI values were computed and visually assessed across representative scenes. Evaluation focused primarily on

the spectral separability of floating materials, while also considering index consistency, dynamic range, and noise levels over water surfaces. Based on these observations, the correction method offering cleaner, more interpretable spectral signatures was selected for downstream model training.

4.3.3 Software Stack & Libraries

This project integrates geospatial and machine learning tools across the processing pipeline:

- **Data acquisition & visualization:** Sentinel-2 imagery was retrieved from the Copernicus Open Access Hub and inspected using QGIS for manual labeling support.
- **Atmospheric correction:** Level-1C scenes were processed with ACOLITE (DSF method) to obtain surface reflectance suitable for spectral index computation.
- **Index generation:** NDVI and FDI maps were computed using `rasterio`, `numpy`, and custom Python scripts.
- **Classification:** Training data was sampled from labeled polygons. An SVM classifier was implemented using `scikit-learn`.
- **Instance segmentation:** RGB image tiling and annotation were performed with `rasterio` and the Roboflow platform. YOLOv11 models were trained via the `ultralytics` library.
- **Evaluation & visualization:** Metrics and outputs were visualized using `matplotlib`, `seaborn`, and `pandas`.

4.3.4 Dataset Preparation Workflow

This project employs two distinct pipelines for preparing training datasets:

- One for spectral index-based classification using spectral index maps
- Another for instance segmentation using RGB composites – TCI product

Each pipeline follows a tailored workflow adapted to the nature of the input data and target output.

4.3.4.1 Pipeline for Supervised Classification

This pipeline focuses on classifying pixels based on computed spectral indices derived from surface reflectance data. One of the key components of this pipeline is the comparative evaluation of atmospheric correction (AC) methods.

Input Data and Atmospheric Correction Comparison Two atmospheric correction approaches were used to prepare Sentinel-2 surface reflectance data:

- **Sen2Cor**-corrected data were obtained directly as Level-2A products. These scenes are already atmospherically corrected and were used as is.
- **ACOLITE DSF**-corrected data were generated by running the ACOLITE software locally on the corresponding Level-1C scenes, using the Dark Spectrum Fitting (DSF) method.

Both correction methods were applied to the same Sentinel-2 granules, i.e., identical acquisition dates and geographic areas, to ensure consistency in further comparative analysis.

Index Computation The NDVI and FDI indices were computed from surface reflectance bands and served as engineered features for the supervised classification task. Due to the spatial resolution of the constituent bands (notably Bands 6 and 11), both indices were generated at a 20-meter resolution. The resulting index rasters were then prepared for labeling and analysis.

Labeling and Sampling The computed index layers were imported into QGIS, where manual labeling was performed.

- Point features were used to annotate small targets such as floating debris.
- Polygon features were used for larger objects and continuous areas such as water bodies or algae blooms.

Each vector annotation was assigned a specific class label (e.g., water, algae, plastic, timber), and these vectors were used as masks to extract the corresponding pixel values from the NDVI and FDI layers. The extracted pixel-level values formed the basis for structured tabular datasets, with each row representing a pixel and its associated indices values and class label.

Atmospheric Correction Method Selection Two separate datasets were generated for each atmospheric correction method (e.g., Sen2Cor and ACOLITE DSF), resulting in two parallel labeled datasets containing NDVI and FDI features. Exploratory data analysis using kdeplots, boxplots, and summary statistics was performed to assess class distributions and separability. These analyses informed the selection of the most appropriate atmospheric correction method for subsequent classification, based on the degree of visual and statistical class separation in the NDVI–FDI feature space.

4.3.5 Label Definitions

To train the supervised classification model, a set of semantic labels was defined based on prior publications and visual interpretation of satellite imagery in selected regions. Most categories are derived from the case studies presented in [Biermann 2020], which serves as a primary reference for this project. The following labels are used:

- **Plastic debris** – Floating synthetic materials such as bags, bottles, and packaging. These often exhibit elevated reflectance in the near-infrared and distinct index behavior, such as low to moderate FDI and low NDVI values.
- **Seaweed (Sargassum)** – Naturally occurring dense organic mats, especially common in Caribbean regions like Barbados. These typically show very high NDVI and moderate FDI due to their strong chlorophyll content and surface aggregation.
- **Timber/logs** – Floating wooden materials (e.g., driftwood), which often appear in the same areas and aggregations as plastic debris. Their co-occurrence makes it essential to account for their spectral signature when modeling the composition of debris patches. Example imagery (included later) illustrates this overlap.
- **Volcanic pumice** – Buoyant rock fragments originating from undersea volcanic activity (e.g., Tonga). These are spectrally and visually distinct due to their texture and lower reflectance.
- **Water** – This class is used to cover the wide variability in natural water surfaces. Rather than selecting only clean, unobstructed water, this class includes samples from diverse water conditions: turbid and clear water, smooth and wavy surfaces, and both shallow and deep areas. This diversity helps the model generalize to different aquatic backgrounds when detecting or classifying floating objects.

Color	Label
	algae
	plastic
	pumice
	seaweed
	timber
	water

Figure 4.8: Classification palette

An additional category, **Algae**, was introduced to capture transitional stages between low-vegetation debris (e.g., plastic, timber) and mature seaweed mats. Floating plastic is frequently colonized by micro- and macro-algae, and this class helps to model objects with moderate NDVI and ambiguous visual signatures, especially in early growth stages.

For the YOLO-based instance segmentation model, only a single class — *debris* is used, encompassing all visually identifiable floating materials such as plastic, timber, algae, and pumice.

Although these materials differ in origin and spectral behavior, they often share similar filament-like shapes and contrast in RGB composites (Fig. 4.9), justifying their treatment as a unified object class during annotation. Material-specific distinctions are addressed separately through the index-based supervised classification pipeline.

4.3.6 Pipeline for Instance Segmentation

This pipeline targets the detection and pixel-level segmentation of debris objects in Sentinel-2 RGB imagery using deep learning.

Data Source and Annotation Setup Since instance segmentation is a computer vision task, it uses True Color Images (TCI) derived from Sentinel-2 bands 4, 3, and 2.

Initial manual inspection in QGIS was used to identify scenes with visually detectable debris. Vectors were drawn around visible objects to guide the tiling process, ensuring that the generated image patches contained relevant content.

Tiling and Annotation RGB scenes were tiled into fixed-size image patches, excluding empty or irrelevant tiles. These tiles were uploaded to the Roboflow

Figure 4.9: Debris samples for segmentation. First row – pumice and timber from Tonga and Japan. Second row - algae and plastic from Omoa

platform for annotation.

Each visible debris object was outlined using polygon masks, with margins to capture surrounding water. This approach avoids the need for pixel-perfect annotations, which are time-consuming and difficult to generate for small or semi-transparent objects.

Dataset Version Creation and Export The Roboflow platform provides the following functionality:

- Cloud storage for user datasets, with access through a Web API
- Train/validation/test splits (with configurable ratios)
- Optional contrast enhancement and resizing
- Exporting in COCO segmentation format, compatible with YOLOv11

This dataset forms the input for model fine-tuning and evaluation in the instance segmentation pipeline.

Methodology Contribution

5.1 Classification Model Pipeline

This section describes the full processing pipeline developed for supervised classification of floating debris using spectral index features derived from Sentinel-2 MSI data.

5.1.1 Input Data and Scene Metadata

The input consists of Sentinel-2 MSI scenes processed to surface reflectance, either directly from Sen2Cor or produced via ACOLITE's Dark Spectrum Fitting (DSF) atmospheric correction. Each scene includes 13 spectral bands and associated metadata, which is used to extract relevant information such as:

- **NoData mask** to exclude invalid pixels,
- **Quantification values and scaling coefficients** to convert digital numbers (DN) into surface (BoA) or top-of-atmosphere (ToA) reflectance values,
- **Scene acquisition metadata** (e.g., sensing date, granule ID) used for exploratory data grouping and scene tracking.

Figure 5.1: FDI and NDVI indices samples with suspected debris, histogram of both images clipped by range $[-1; 1]$

5.1.2 Feature Extraction

Two spectral indices are computed from valid surface reflectance values:

- NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)
- FDI (Floating Debris Index)

These indices are calculated only for pixels within a valid reflectance range of $[0, 1]$ and not flagged as NoData.

The output consists of two single-band rasters per scene, representing NDVI and FDI values.

5.1.3 Label Creation

Labels for training data are manually created in QGIS (Fig. 5.1). A separate vector file (in GeoJSON format) is prepared for each label class (e.g., plastic, algae, timber, pumice, water), based on visual interpretation and contextual information. Point or polygon features are drawn over locations with known or suspected material presence.

Figure 5.2: Example of labeling suspected debris (plastic) by point and water samples by polygon geometries on FDI index raster data

5.1.4 Sample Extraction and Tabular Dataset Generation

Each label vector file is rasterized to a pixel mask, aligned with the corresponding index raster.

The masked index values are extracted and flattened, then stored as rows in a unified CSV table with the following structure:

```
region_name
scene_id
NDVI_value
FDI_value
label
```

The `region_name` and `scene_id` columns are used during exploratory analysis to assess how spectral signatures vary by location and acquisition date, supporting later dataset refinement.

Figure 5.3: Extracted water and plastic FDI samples by rasterized label geometries

5.1.5 Atmospheric Correction Methods Selection

This section presents a comparative evaluation of two atmospheric correction (AC) methods – **Sen2Cor** and **ACOLITE DSF** applied to the same set of Sentinel-2 scenes. All preprocessing steps, including NDVI and FDI index computation, label rasterization, and pixel value extraction, were conducted identically for both datasets to ensure comparability. Importantly, this analysis was performed on raw, unfiltered data; no outlier removal or resampling procedures were applied at this stage in order to reflect the native behavior of each AC method.

Comparative Analysis of Feature Distributions (Boxplots)

Boxplots of NDVI and FDI (Figs. 5.4, 5.5), grouped by class, were used to evaluate how the two atmospheric correction methods affect value distributions and potential class separability.

- **Water:** Both methods show a wide NDVI distribution, reflecting high variability in water surface conditions (e.g., turbidity, wave patterns). However, ACOLITE reduces the NDVI spread by nearly 50%, narrowing the whisker range from approximately $[-1, 0.6]$ under Sen2Cor to $[-0.5, 0.25]$.

Figure 5.4: Boxplots of Sen2Cor method

This compression, along with a slight shift of the mean toward zero, suggests improved spectral consistency. FDI remains tightly centered near zero in both cases, with moderate upper-end outliers.

- **Pumice:** Both NDVI and FDI distributions are compact and nearly identical across methods (NDVI centered around -0.1 , FDI ~ 0.02), indicating that pumice’s spectral signature is stable and minimally impacted by atmospheric correction.
- **Plastic and Timber:** NDVI distributions for plastic and timber are more distinguishable under Sen2Cor, with plastic centered around 0.2 and timber around 0.26. While some overlap exists, it is moderate. In contrast, ACOLITE shifts both means closer (to approximately 0.25) and compresses the NDVI range, resulting in almost complete overlap between the two classes. In FDI space, both plastic and timber also shift closer to the water distribution under ACOLITE, further reducing their separability. This “submergence” in spectral space suggests that ACOLITE may weaken class contrast for these debris types, especially when compared to Sen2Cor’s slightly broader but better-separated distributions.
- **Algae:** NDVI is more tightly distributed and higher under ACOLITE (mean ~ 0.55) than Sen2Cor (~ 0.46), enhancing its separation from non-vegetative classes. FDI under ACOLITE is also more compact, though some overlap with plastic and timber remains. Overall, algae appears better isolated in ACOLITE, particularly in NDVI space.

Figure 5.5: Boxplots of ACOLITE DSF method

- **Seaweed:** Seaweed shows the most pronounced difference: NDVI values under ACOLITE are significantly higher (mean ~ 0.8 vs. 0.56 in Sen2Cor) and more compact, while FDI is also tighter. This suggests that ACOLITE enhances seaweed’s spectral contrast, likely due to improved correction in near-infrared wavelengths.

KDE-Based Class Separation Analysis

To validate the visual patterns observed in the KDE plot (Fig. 5.6), Mahalanobis and Bhattacharyya distances were computed between key class pairs for both Sen2Cor and ACOLITE DSF corrected datasets (see Table 5.1).

These metrics provide a quantitative assessment of class separability in the NDVI–FDI feature space.

The results confirm and support the qualitative observations:

- Vegetation-related classes, especially algae and seaweed, show substantially higher separation under ACOLITE. The algae–seaweed Bhattacharyya distance increases from 2.20 (Sen2Cor) to 4.21 (ACOLITE), and the Mahalanobis distance from 3.84 to 5.49 , indicating a clear enhancement in spectral distinctness.
- A moderate increase in plastic–algae separation is also observed (Bhattacharyya: $2.86 \rightarrow 3.52$, Mahalanobis: $4.25 \rightarrow 4.76$), supporting the idea that vegetation vs. debris contrast is better under ACOLITE.

Figure 5.6: KDE plot in NDVI-FDI feature space for explored AC methods

- In contrast, the plastic–timber pair shows a significant loss of separability under ACOLITE:
 - Mahalanobis distance drops from 2.31 to 1.10
 - Bhattacharyya distance drops from 0.995 to 0.427

This confirms the strong overlap observed in KDE and boxplot visualizations, indicating that Sen2Cor is more effective at distinguishing between these mid-range debris classes.

- Other class pairs, such as plastic–pumice, show only marginal changes (Bhattacharyya: 2.77 \rightarrow 3.58), suggesting that separability remains comparable between methods for these combinations.

In summary, the distance metrics corroborate the KDE-based insights: ACOLITE DSF enhances separability for vegetative classes, particularly algae and seaweed, while Sen2Cor maintains stronger separation between spectrally similar debris types, such as plastic and timber.

Given that plastic detection is a central objective of this study, and that Sen2Cor better preserves its distinction from both timber and water, it was selected as the preferred atmospheric correction method for the classification task.

Class Pair	Mahalanobis (Sen2Cor)	Mahalanobis (ACOLITE)	Bhatt (Sen2Cor)	Bhatt (ACOLITE)
Plastic – Timber	2.311	1.104	0.995	0.427
Plastic – Water	2.090	2.678	1.524	1.439
Plastic – Pumice	3.816	4.286	2.773	3.582
Plastic – Algae	4.251	4.765	2.862	3.520
Timber – Algae	4.311	6.318	2.555	5.239
Timber – Water	4.034	3.216	3.702	2.366
Pumice – Water	2.560	3.024	2.445	2.784
Algae – Seaweed	3.841	5.493	2.204	4.210

Table 5.1: Class separability metrics (Mahalanobis and Bhattacharyya distances) under Sen2Cor or ACOLITE DSF corrections.

Model Training and Evaluation

The model training process follows a structured refinement pipeline designed to improve input data (Fig. 5.7) quality and maximize classification performance, particularly for the plastic class, which is the main target of the study:

- 1. Pre-filtering of saturated and extreme values:**

We begin by removing samples with NDVI values equal to -1 or 1 , as these typically correspond to invalid or saturated reflectance values. For the water class, we also exclude samples with NDVI below -0.2 , as these values extend well beyond the main cluster region shared by other classes in the NDVI–FDI space. By filtering these deep-tail values, we retain water samples that lie closer to debris and vegetation classes, which are more informative for defining meaningful decision boundaries.

- 2. Outlier removal using Isolation Forest:**

Next, we apply an Isolation Forest (with contamination = 0.05) to the remaining dataset. This unsupervised algorithm identifies outliers in the NDVI–FDI feature space by recursively isolating anomalous samples. This step helps remove mislabeled points and mixed pixels caused by imperfect raster–vector alignment or label noise.

- 3. Class balancing based on plastic-to-others ratio:**

To prevent the classifier from being biased toward majority classes (e.g., water, algae), we perform class balancing based on a fixed ratio. Specifically, the number of samples in each majority class is limited to at most twice the number of plastic samples (1:2 ratio).

Figure 5.7: Scatterplot for raw Sen2Cor input data. Scenes were also encoded to refine dataset in future if needed.

Label	Raw	Filtered and Balanced
Water	159514	376
Pumice	14080	376
Seaweed	2201	376
Algae	672	376
Timber	489	376
Plastic	198	188

Table 5.2: Sample counts before and after filtering and class balancing.

This ensures that plastic, as the target class, is not overwhelmed during training, while still preserving a reasonable number of samples from other categories to maintain boundary diversity.

4. Classifier Definition

A Support Vector Classifier (SVC) with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel is trained on the preprocessed dataset (Fig. 5.8). The following hyperparameters are used:

- kernel='rbf'
- gamma=1000
- class_weight='balanced'

The high gamma value produces a highly non-linear decision surface (Fig. 5.9), intentionally overfitting the labeled data to capture fine-grained class

Figure 5.8: Scatter plot of the preprocessed dataset in the NDVI–FDI feature space after applying NDVI saturation filtering, Isolation Forest-based outlier removal, and class balancing.

boundaries. These hyperparameters support the overfitting strategy outlined in the planning chapter, allowing the model to focus on reproducing class-specific spectral patterns within the NDVI–FDI space rather than aiming for broad generalization. Take a mention that water becomes “background” label here.

To account for a slight class imbalance, the `class_weight='balanced'` parameter automatically adjusts class-specific penalty terms. Specifically, it sets the weight of class i to:

$$\text{class_weight}_i = \frac{n_{\text{samples}}}{n_{\text{classes}} \cdot \text{count}(y_i)}$$

This ensures that plastic class, contribute proportionally more to the optimization objective, improving the definition of decision boundaries around rare or ambiguous samples.

5. Iterative validation and manual correction:

After each training round, predictions were checked on selected subre-

Figure 5.9: Decision boundaries of the Support Vector Classifier (SVC) with RBF kernel in the NDVI–FDI feature space.

gions from different scenes. Misclassified areas especially false positives in water were manually reviewed, and new water samples were added to reduce over-detection. For example (Fig. 5.8), water samples with values > 0.2 of NDVI were added in dataset, to improve discriminative performance between timber and background water.

5.2 Instance Segmentation Model

The second methodological pipeline addresses the problem of object-based debris detection using instance segmentation. This pipeline centers on training YOLOv11 segmentation models using custom-annotated imagery derived from Sentinel-2 TCI composites.

Dataset Generation and Preprocessing To build the training dataset, debris containing regions were first manually identified using NDVI, FDI index maps and TCI visual composites in QGIS. These regions were roughly annotated us-

ing polygons (Fig. 5.10), serving as spatial masks to generate a grid of tiles (512×512 pixels) from each scene. Each tile was saved in JPEG format with an accompanying world file (.jgw) to retain geospatial reference when needed. This process produced a total of 787 tiles, which were uploaded to the Roboflow

Figure 5.10: Example of manual annotation of suspected debris for further tiling.

platform for manual annotation. Every suspected debris object was outlined using polygon vector masks and assigned a single class label: debris.

The dataset was split into 591 training, 119 validation, and 77 test tiles. To improve the learning process for small and faint objects, Roboflow applied contrast stretching (Fig. 5.11) and upsampled each image to 768×768 pixels. Additionally, 254 background only tiles (no debris present) were included to improve debris separation from background signature.

Class Name	Total Count	Training Count	Validation Count	Test Count
debris	2192	1748	249	195

Table 5.3: Overview of number of debris annotations for each split.

The final annotated dataset was exported in COCO segmentation format, then, at the training stage, will be converted to the YOLOv11 compatible structure with the appropriate `train/`, `valid/`, and `test/` directories, annotation `.txt` files, and a dataset `.yaml` configuration file.

Figure 5.11: Example of annotated tiles with contrast enhancing.

Model Variants and Training Configuration

Three YOLOv11 instance segmentation model sizes were trained:

- YOLOv11n-seg (nano)
- YOLOv11s-seg (small)
- YOLOv11m-seg (medium)

Each was initialized with pretrained weights and trained under the same hyperparameter configuration to ensure consistency and comparability:

- Epochs: 100
- Image size: 768×768
- Optimizer: AdamW
- Learning rates: $1e-4$ and $1e-5$ (used in different runs)
- Learning rate scheduler: Cosine
- Frozen layers: 0 or 10 frozen layers (Backbone frozen or not)
- Batch size: 8
- Single class: Enabled (`single_cls=True`)
- Mixup: Disabled for segmentation (`mixup=0.0`)

Figure 5.12: Example of mosaic (left picture) and copy-paste (right picture) data augmentation procedures during model training.

Key augmentations used during training:

- `mosaic=0.5`: Combines four different training images into one (Fig. 5.12), simulating varied scene layouts and object interactions. Especially useful for object detection and segmentation in complex and cluttered scenes.
- `copy_paste=1.0`: Artificially increases the number of object instances by copying segmented debris objects and pasting them into other images (Fig. 5.12), improving model generalization.
- `copy_paste_mode='mixup'`: Specifies the strategy used during copy-paste augmentation. In this configuration, mixup blending is used when pasting copied objects, helping the model adapt to different lighting, textures, and boundary conditions.

5.3 Evaluation Strategy — Segmentation Model

The performance of the YOLOv11 instance segmentation models is assessed using a set of COCO-style metrics that evaluate both bounding box and segmentation mask predictions. Three key metrics are calculated for each output type (box and mask):

- **mAP50**: Mean Average Precision at an IoU threshold of 0.5. This metric measures how accurately the model localizes and segments objects with moderate overlap.

- **mAP50-95:** The average of mAP values computed at IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0.95 in steps of 0.05. This provides a more stringent assessment of model robustness across varying overlap levels.
- **Recall:** The proportion of ground truth annotations that are correctly predicted by the model. This helps identify the rate of missed detections (false negatives), which is especially important in this pipeline — since the segmentation output is later passed to a classification model that can refine or filter false positives.

Each trained variant of YOLO model – nano, small, and medium – is evaluated using these metrics on the validation subset, which is defined in the `data.yaml` file and automatically used by the training process. All reported metrics and training plots are based on this validation data.

The selection of the best segmentation model follows a cascading evaluation strategy:

1. **Intra-model selection:**

For each model size (e.g., `yolov11n-seg`, `yolov11s-seg`, `yolov11m-seg`), multiple configurations with different hyperparameters (e.g., learning rate, frozen layers) are trained. The best-performing configuration is selected based on validation mAP and recall metrics.

2. **Inter-model comparison:**

Once the best configuration is selected for each model size, a second round of comparison is conducted between these top variants to identify the overall best-performing segmentation model.

Although segmentation mask performance is the primary criterion for model selection, bounding box metrics are also considered. This is because bounding boxes provide useful localization priors and may still contribute meaningfully to downstream workflows — for instance, identifying object regions to extract additional features for SVM-based classification.

5.4 Evaluation Strategy — Classification Model

The evaluation of the SVM-based classification model was carried out using both formal accuracy metrics and practical segmentation mask based validation to assess its performance in real-world scenarios.

5.4.1 Formal Assessment Using Test Subset

The primary evaluation metric was the confusion matrix, computed on a hold-out test subset. This matrix provides a detailed view of how well the classifier distinguishes between the six defined classes: plastic, algae, timber, seaweed, pumice, and water. From the confusion matrix, standard classification metrics were derived, including:

- Overall accuracy
- Per-class precision, recall, and F1-score

These metrics serve primarily as a basic validation of model training, confirming that the classifier correctly separates clearly distinct classes using only NDVI and FDI features. Since these materials are generally spectrally separable, this evaluation does not reflect real-world complexity, but ensures that the model has learned a meaningful decision boundary.

5.4.2 Object-Level Assessment on Real Scenes

To evaluate the classification model's performance under realistic conditions, we implement an object-level assessment strategy that uses not only the curated validation set (as defined in the methodology) but also additional scenes drawn from the segmentation model's test split. This broader test scope allows us to analyze how well the classifier performs in conjunction with the outputs of the instance segmentation model.

Formation of the Evaluation Dataset

For each selected scene, we construct a validation dataset at the object level using the following three label sources:

1. **Predicted class labels** – The full set of categories predicted by the classifier (e.g., plastics, timber, algae, etc.).
2. **Manual annotations** – Human-labeled masks (Fig. 5.13) identifying debris regions. These are treated as binary masks (debris vs water) and serve as the reference ground truth where available.
3. **Segmentation masks** – Debris predictions from the YOLOv11 segmentation model, also treated as binary (debris vs background/water).

Some scenes do not include manual annotations. In these cases, a quantitative assessment is not feasible due to factors such as:

Figure 5.13: Example of manual annotation using FDI index.

- High object density,
- Complex or semi-transparent shapes,
- Ambiguity in object boundaries.

Such scenes are instead assessed visually, focusing on qualitative evaluation of classifier behavior across different debris types and contexts.

5.4.3 Two-Stage Evaluation Strategy

To analyze the impact of segmentation filtering on classification results next two-stage evaluation protocol was proposed:

1. Raw Evaluation (Classifier Alone)

This stage evaluates the performance of the classifier independently, without applying any filtering from the segmentation mask.

For each validation scene, the following diagnostic metrics are computed:

- Precision: The proportion of predicted debris pixels that are true debris (i.e., low precision indicates many false positives).

- Recall: The proportion of ground truth debris pixels correctly predicted as debris (i.e., low recall indicates many false negatives).
- F1-Score: Harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced measure of classifier effectiveness.
- False Positive Composition: The class distribution of pixels falsely predicted as debris, useful to identify systematic confusions (e.g., water surface ripples being misclassified as pumice or plastic).
- Predicted Debris Composition: The breakdown of predicted class labels over true debris pixels, evaluating the model's ability to estimate debris type correctly.

2. Evaluation with Segmentation - Filtering

In the second stage, classifier predictions are filtered using the segmentation masks. Specifically:

- Any object predicted by the classifier is retained in the evaluation, but its label is overridden as “water” if it falls outside the segmented debris masks.

This simulates the real-world use case where the classifier receives input that has already passed through the segmentation model. The goal is to measure whether segmentation filtering helps reduce false positives and how it affects overall performance, particularly for background suppression.

This chapter presents the results of the proposed debris detection pipeline and is structured in two main parts: (1) training and evaluation of the instance segmentation model (YOLOv11) for identifying debris patches, and (2) performance assessment of the supervised classification model (SVM) for estimating debris composition within segmented patches. Validation is conducted across diverse sites to examine model robustness under varying debris types and environmental conditions.

6.1 Segmentation Model Results

The segmentation model evaluation followed a two-stage selection approach:

1. Intra-model hyperparameter search to select the best configuration for each model size.
2. Cross-model comparison to select the final architecture.

Each model was evaluated based on training and validation curves. For every model variant, two plots are presented:

- **Training Curves:** tracking box loss, segmentation loss, classification loss, and distribution focal loss (DFL), separately for training and validation data.
- **Performance Metrics:** showing bounding box and mask metrics over epochs — including precision, recall, mAP50, and mAP50-95.

6.1.1 Intra-model Selection

For each model size (e.g., yolov11n-seg, yolov11s-seg, yolov11m-seg), the best configuration was chosen based on mask/box mAPs and recall metrics.

Nano model size – yolov11n-seg For this model configuration (Fig. 6.1 and 6.2), values $lr0 = 0.0001$, $freeze = 0$ clearly show better performance across all metrics, except for precision (B), where it performs equally well as configurations $lr0 = 0.00001$, $freeze = 0$ and $lr0 = 0.0001$, $freeze = 10$.

Figure 6.1: Performance plots for yolov11n-seg model size.

Figure 6.2: Training plots for yolov11n-seg model size.

Small model size – yolov11s-seg For this model configuration (Fig. 6.3 and 6.4), values $lr0 = 0.0001$ and $freeze = 0$ demonstrate slightly better overall performance compared to other configurations. Although its mAP50–95 (Box) is marginally lower than that of the $lr0 = 0.00001$, $freeze = 0$ configuration.

Figure 6.3: Performance plots for yolov11s-seg model size.

Figure 6.4: Training plots for yolov11s-seg model size.

Medium model size – yolov11m-seg For this model size (Fig. 6.5 and 6.6), the configuration with $lr0 = 0.0001$ and $freeze = 0$ demonstrates clear improvements in mAP50–95 for both Box and Mask predictions, along with slightly better recall values for both tasks compared to other configurations.

Figure 6.5: Performance plots for yolov11m-seg model size.

Figure 6.6: Training plots for yolov11m-seg model size.

Cross-model Comparison

In the second stage, the top configurations from each model size were compared side by side (Figs. 6.7 and 6.8). Again, model performance plots guided the final selection.

Figure 6.7: Cross-model performance comparison plots.

Figure 6.8: Cross-model training comparison plots.

The quantitative comparison of the final segmentation models across different YOLOv11 sizes (nano, small, medium) is summarized in the Table 6.1, using box and mask metrics evaluated on the valid split.

Size	Box				Mask			
	Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50-95
nano	0.464	0.454	0.377	0.186	0.379	0.321	0.260	0.064
small	0.481	0.442	0.414	0.182	0.347	0.360	0.259	0.069
medium	0.450	0.506	0.416	0.214	0.348	0.345	0.259	0.074

Table 6.1: Summary of box and mask metrics for YOLOv11 models of different sizes (nano, small, medium), evaluated on the validation split.

Among the three model sizes, the medium sized configuration demonstrates superior overall performance, with the highest values for both Recall and mAP50–95 (Box and Mask). The only exception is mAP50 (Mask), where it performs on par with the smaller models. This makes the medium-sized model the most effective choice for segmentation in this study.

6.1.2 Test Split Performance

Following model selection based on validation results, we evaluated the chosen medium-sized model on the test split. This final evaluation provides an unbiased estimate of the model’s performance on previously unseen data.

To further illustrate the model’s performance on the test split (Fig. 6.9), three representative examples are presented. The first image depicts a pumice-dominated scenario, where the model successfully detected and segmented most debris objects, demonstrating strong generalization to complex textures. The second image shows a false negative case, where the model failed to detect debris that is only faintly visible against the background, illustrating challenges in identifying subtle or low-contrast fragments. The third image presents another successful detection, with accurate segmentation of debris and minimal false positives, confirming the model’s robustness under clearer conditions.

Figure 6.9: Example of segmentation on test split images, top row are labels, bottom predicted masks.

Comparison with COCO-Seg baseline performance.

Box				Mask			
Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50-95
0.452	0.421	0.380	0.197	0.353	0.328	0.254	0.061

Table 6.2: Performance metrics of fine-tuned model validated on test split.

Compared to the baseline benchmark metrics of the YOLOv11-seg medium model, which reports:

- mAP50-95 Box: 51.5
- mAP50-95 Mask: 41.5

Our selected model achieves 19.7 (Box) and 6.1 (Mask) on the test split (Table 6.2). While the gap in performance highlights the inherent challenges of detecting marine debris in satellite imagery such as low contrast, small object size, and partial submersion these results are still acceptable within the context of our pipeline.

Unlike general-purpose object detection benchmarks, our objective is not precise segmentation but rather the generation of coarse spatial priors to support a downstream classification model. In this setup, even modest mAP scores are sufficient, as the segmentation model's role is to filter and narrow the search space, effectively guiding the classifier toward more relevant regions and improving the overall debris detection process.

6.1.3 Evaluation on Validation Sites

The generalization capacity of the final segmentation model was explored using external validation scenes introduced in the methodology (Chapter 4). Specifically, qualitative analysis was conducted over two distinct regions: the coastal waters of Durban, South Africa, where plastic debris is prevalent, and Okinawa, Japan, known for floating timber aggregations.

Examples from the Durban area illustrate both the strengths and limitations of the model. In one case, the segmentation accurately captures (Fig. 6.11) a plastics aggregation despite partial cloud cover, with only minor omissions beneath semi-transparent cirrus. Another example shows confusion between debris and textured cloud formations (Fig. 6.10), resulting in a false detection.

Figure 6.10: False positive example of cloud segmentation, Durban coastal area.

Figure 6.11: Plastics segmentation, Durban coastal area.

A third scene (Fig. 6.12) highlights a false positive, where the model mistakenly segments the diagonal border of an internal MSI sensor frame.

Figure 6.12: False positive example, Durban coastal area.

Figure 6.13: False positive on foam, Okinawa shoreline.

Further evaluation in the Okinawa region provides additional insight into model behavior in complex marine environments. In one scene (Fig. 6.13), the model performs well overall: distinct debris objects are correctly segmented despite the challenging presence of clouds, shoreline, and foam-like formations. A minor false positive occurs where the model confuses foam patterns with debris.

Another example (Fig. 6.14) highlights a failure case: the model misses distinct, hair-like pumice formations in the lower right part of the tile image, an error likely stemming from the absence of similar shapes in the training data.

Lastly, in a visually dense scene (Fig. 6.15) containing islands, boats, and boat trails, the model exhibits over-segmentation – detecting multiple objects,

Figure 6.14: False negative example, Okinawa coastal area.

Figure 6.15: False positive examples, Okinawa shoreline.

including false positives such as island roads and wake trails from moving vessels. These observations confirm that the model remains generally reliable across diverse conditions and continues to serve its role effectively in generating spatial priors for downstream classification.

6.2 Supervised Classification Results

6.2.1 Confusion Matrix and Overall Performance

The supervised classifier achieved strong results on the test split (Table 6.3), with a balanced accuracy of 0.972 and a macro-averaged F1-score of 0.973. All classes were classified with high precision and recall, including perfect scores for seaweed, and nearly perfect scores for algae and timber. Despite the limited size of the test set, these results reflect a well-refined dataset and a model trained under overfitting conditions, optimized to closely match the training distribution.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
algae	1.000	0.991	0.996	113
plastic	0.964	0.946	0.955	56
pumice	0.919	1.000	0.958	113
seaweed	1.000	1.000	1.000	113
timber	0.982	0.982	0.982	113
water	0.981	0.912	0.945	113
accuracy			0.974	621
balanced accuracy			0.972	621
macro avg	0.974	0.972	0.973	621
weighted avg	0.975	0.974	0.974	621

Table 6.3: Classification performance metrics for each class in the test dataset.

Despite the high overall performance, the confusion matrix (Fig. 6.16) reveals a few systematic misclassifications. The most prominent occurs between pumice and water: the classifier correctly identifies all pumice samples (recall = 1.000), but incorrectly labels 10 water samples as pumice. This likely stems from pumice’s physical property of absorbing and retaining water, which can give it a similar spectral signature in the FDI – NDVI feature space.

Further, plastic is occasionally misclassified as timber or water, reflecting minor spectral ambiguity or edge effects in those samples. Timber and algae each show a single misclassification, both involving plastic, while seaweed is predicted perfectly.

These errors, though rare, underscore that the model’s decisions are strongly shaped by the characteristics of the training dataset. While this setup results in very high accuracy on the test split, it may limit robustness to novel or more ambiguous inputs in operational use.

Figure 6.16: Confusion matrix with per-class classification performance.

6.2.2 Evaluation on Segmentation-Derived Regions

To evaluate the classifier on real-world imagery, predictions were generated for several independent scenes introduced in Chapter 4. These include three validation sites: Durban (South Africa), where plastic debris was expected; Visegrad Dam (Bosnia and Herzegovina), containing a mix of plastic and timber; and Okinawa (Japan), where pumice was anticipated.

In addition, two test tiles from the segmentation dataset were used: New Zealand, associated with timber, and Omoa, featuring plastic and algae. All of these datasets originate from the previous stage of the pipeline — segmentation model outputs, so corresponding segmentation masks were available to guide classification.

Visegrád Dam - Example

This example demonstrates the classification performance near the **Visegrád Dam**, where distinct debris formations are visible floating close to the dam structure (Fig. 6.17, panel A). In this case, a vectorized water surface boundary derived from the OpenStreetMap (OSM) database (Fig. 6.17, panel B) is used as the segmentation mask, which serves the same role as the segmentation mask in other examples: it adjusts predictions by excluding detections outside the segmented debris location.

The raw classification output (Fig. 6.17, panel C) reveals a large number of false positives, particularly over bright cloud features mistakenly identified as debris. After applying the OSM-derived water mask (Fig. 6.17, panel D), these

Figure 6.17: Debris classification at Visegrád Dam. Panel A - input image to classify. Panel B - segmentation mask (derived from OSM) and manually annotated debris (pink dots). Panel C - raw predictions. Panel D - adjusted predictions.

spurious detections are effectively removed, yielding a cleaner and more geographically coherent prediction map focused on the actual water body.

The diagnostic plots (Fig. 6.18) illustrate classification performance before and after applying the OSM-derived vector mask, which serves as the segmentation mask in the current example.

Figure 6.18: Debris Classification on Visegrad Dam – Before (first row) and After (second row) Segmentation Adjustment.

In the first row, which shows raw classification results, the false positive composition is dominated by plastic (62%), largely due to misclassifications over

cloud-covered areas. The precision is low at 0.167, while recall remains high at 0.882, resulting in an F1 score of 0.281. This reflects the model's tendency to overpredict debris presence in visually complex regions like clouds.

In the second row, after adjusting predictions using the vectorized water mask, most false detections outside the water body are removed. The remaining false positives are now mostly labeled as pumice, which appears to be a model-specific confusion. Precision improves significantly to 0.778, while recall remains unchanged at 0.882, as all manually annotated debris falls within the valid water extent. The resulting F1 score rises to 0.827, indicating a much more balanced and reliable performance after spatial filtering.

Ground truth debris composition consists of approximately 63% timber, 25% plastic, and 12% water. This distribution aligns well with multiple media reports from the same period, which described large accumulations of wood debris floating near the dam after upstream flooding events.

Durban – Example 1

In the first Durban example (Fig. 6.19), the input scene is affected by cloud cover, with debris patches barely visible in the RGB composite.

Figure 6.19: Debris classification on Durban, example 1. Panel A - input image to classify. Panel B - segmentation mask and manually annotated debris (orange dots). Panel C - raw predictions. Panel D - adjusted predictions.

One of the debris formations is only clearly detectable in the FDI index, causing the segmentation model to miss it entirely (Fig. 6.19, panel B, lower left corner). The classifier, however, produces (Fig. 6.19, panel C) numerous false positives, especially plastic and pumice on clouds and thin cirrus.

In the diagnostic plots (Fig. 6.20), the first row (raw predictions) shows a high number of false positives dominated by plastic and pumice. Precision is very low at 0.003, while recall is relatively high (0.757) since the classifier successfully detects debris at both known locations. The resulting F1-score is 0.005.

Figure 6.20: Debris Classification on Durban, example 1 – Before (first row) and After (second row) Segmentation Adjustment.

After applying the segmentation mask (second row), most false positives are eliminated, but recall drops due to the missed segmentation of one debris patch. False positives now consist entirely of pumice. Precision improves significantly to 0.675, recall drops to 0.365, and F1-score rises to 0.474.

The predicted composition of ground truth debris pixels includes 58% plastic, 18% pumice, and 24% water. This composition helps explain the low recall score: nearly 25% of ground truth debris pixels were misclassified as background, and some debris patches were not captured by the segmentation mask. Together, these factors significantly reduce the model's ability to recover all true debris instances.

Durban – Example 2

In the second example (Fig. 6.21) from the Durban area, the scene is again affected by thin cirrus clouds, leading to numerous false positive detections by the classifier. The segmentation model also made an error: it produced a false

Figure 6.21: Debris classification on Durban, example 2. Panel A - input image to classify. Panel B - segmentation mask and manually annotated debris (brown dots). Panel C - raw predictions. Panel D - adjusted predictions.

positive region, while simultaneously missing part of the actual debris, resulting in a false negative.

Figure 6.22: Debris Classification on Durban, example 2 – Before (first row) and After (second row) Segmentation Adjustment.

Diagnostic plots (Fig. 6.22) for this example show the following:

In the first row (raw predictions), false positives are composed of 58% plastic and 42% pumice, driven largely by cloud-related misclassifications. The perfor-

mance metrics reflect this noise, with a precision of 0.002, recall of 0.906, and F1-score of 0.003 — the model successfully hits almost all ground truth debris but makes overwhelming false detections.

In the second row (adjusted predictions using the segmentation mask), false positives are now mostly pumice (57%) and plastic (42%). Precision improves to 0.133, recall drops to 0.642 due to segmentation errors, and the F1-score increases to 0.220.

The predicted composition of ground truth debris pixels is 84% plastic, with the remainder split between pumice and water — suggesting good class-wise detection, but overall performance is still affected by cloud interference and segmentation inaccuracies.

Figure 6.23: Debris classification on Durban, example 3. Panel A - input image to classify. Panel B - segmentation mask and manually annotated debris (orange dots). Panel C - raw predictions. Panel D - adjusted predictions.

Durban – Example 3

In this third example (Fig. 6.23), the scene is again affected by clouds and thin cirrus, resulting in numerous false detections over these areas.

Despite these conditions, the segmentation model performs relatively well, capturing most of the suspected debris patch. A small portion was missed due

to semitransparent cloud cover. Additionally, the model initially segmented the same debris area in two overlapping parts, which were later merged during post-processing to form a single debris mask.

Figure 6.24: Debris Classification on Durban, example 3 – Before (first row) and After (second row) Segmentation Adjustment.

In terms of diagnostic results (Fig. 6.24) for this example:

In the first row (raw predictions), false positives are primarily plastic (55%) and pumice (42%), with small contributions from algae and timber (>2%) over land surfaces. The precision is extremely low at 0.004, while recall remains relatively high at 0.725, resulting in a very low F1-score of 0.009.

In the second row (adjusted predictions), false positives are again dominated by pumice (58%) and plastic (42%). After adjustment, precision improves to 0.3, recall drops to 0.463 due to partial segmentation, and the F1-score increases to 0.364.

The predicted composition for ground truth debris pixels consists of 50% plastic, 22% pumice, and 28% water, showing that the model had to distinguish between mixed debris types, with a significant water component contributing to potential false negatives.

Durban – Conclusions

This validation site clearly illustrates the challenges posed by cloud-contaminated scenes. Both the segmentation and classification models struggle under these conditions, producing numerous false positives particularly over clouds and thin cirrus, and false negatives where debris is partially obscured. Segmentation misses and background misclassifications (e.g., water labeled instead of debris) further reduce recall.

Despite these difficulties, the classifier still manages to detect debris in most cases, but with very low precision. These results highlight the significant impact of atmospheric conditions on detection performance and the need for improved cloud filtering or correction strategies.

Figure 6.25: Suspected pumice classification on Okinawa, Japan, example 1.

Okinawa – Example 1

This scene (Fig. 6.25) shows a suspected pumice origin debris accumulation in a coastal area. Although no manual ground truth labels are available for quantitative assessment, visual analysis suggests generally good segmentation performance. Most debris patches were detected, though some portions were missed, and false positives appeared on wave foam formations. The classification model predicts a large quantity of pumice, however, some of these predictions likely represent model noise, due to the classifier's tendency to assign pumice labels to water spectrum pixels with low FDI signal. Importantly, the classifier also detects a notable share of plastic-like signatures, which may indicate a mixed debris composition in the coastal area.

Figure 6.26: Suspected pumice classification on Okinawa, Japan, example 2.

Okinawa – Example 2

In this coastal scene (Fig. 6.26), the segmentation model shows weaker performance, failing to detect the central debris formations entirely. This may be due to their thin, hair-like shape, which is underrepresented in the training dataset, making them harder for the model to learn and identify. Despite this, the classification model detects several pixels with a plastic-like spectral signature in the same areas, suggesting potential presence of plastic or mixed-material debris and providing valuable supporting evidence even when segmentation fails.

Okinawa – Conclusions

In conclusion, the Okinawa site shows mixed results: segmentation struggles with thin, dispersed debris, while the classifier detects widespread pumice signals. This likely reflects actual pumice dispersion in coastal waters, but some detections may also be false positives due to spectral similarity to water class.

New Zealand – Example

In this example (Fig. 6.27), suspected timber origin debris is analyzed. The segmentation model performs exceptionally well, capturing nearly all visible debris formations.

Figure 6.27: Suspected timber debris classification on New Zealand.

Notably, the manual annotations were applied in a “greedy” manner, labeling almost all bright pixels on the FDI index as debris, which may have led the classification model to produce a significant number of false negatives—especially confusing low-FDI plastic and timber pixels with water due to their spectral similarity.

In the diagnostic plot (Fig. 6.28), for the raw classifier output, precision is 0.754, meaning 75% of predicted debris are correct, and recall is 0.482, indicating that only 48% of actual debris were detected. The F1-score is 0.588, reflecting a moderate balance between false positives and false negatives. After segmentation filtering, precision improves to 0.860, indicating fewer false positives, while recall slightly drops to 0.450 due to the exhaustive manual labeling. This results in a modest F1-score increase to 0.591, suggesting improved overall performance despite the classification challenges posed by low-FDI plastic and timber being spectrally similar to water.

Figure 6.28: Debris Classification on New Zealand – Before (first row) and After (second row) Segmentation Adjustment.

The predicted composition of ground-truth debris is 51% water, 27% plastic, 12% pumice, and 7.3% timber supports the presence of timber components, especially in the most concentrated debris areas.

New Zealand – Conclusion

Overall, the segmentation and classification models show good performance on this site. However, the false negative rate increased due to exhaustive manual labeling, which included many low-contrast debris pixels with spectral signatures similar to water, challenging the classifier.

Omoa Bay, Honduras – Example 1

This validation site (Fig. 6.29) features suspected algae and seaweed debris. The segmentation model performs well, correctly outlining most debris patches. However, the raw classification model (before segmentation adjustment) produces a high number of false positives, mainly detecting pumice (62%) and plastic (37%) likely caused by water surface ripples are making noise signals.

Figure 6.29: Suspected algae-seaweed debris classification on Omoa Bay, Honduras, example 1.

As shown in the first row of the diagnostic plots (Fig. 6.30), this results in very high recall (0.987) but extremely low precision (0.022), meaning the model detects nearly all actual debris but also mislabels many non-debris pixels. The overall f1-score (0.043) reflects the imbalance.

After segmentation adjustment, shown in the second row, false positives are still dominated by plastic (53%) and pumice (45%), but precision improves significantly to 0.38, while recall slightly drops to 0.871, leading to a much more balanced f1-score of 0.529. This highlights the importance of segmentation filtering in reducing noise and refining the classifier's outputs.

The annotated ground truth debris consists of algae (35%), plastic (34%), and timber (25%), supporting the interpretation of this patch as vegetation-origin marine debris.

Figure 6.30: Debris Classification on Omoa Bay, Honduras, example 1 – Before (first row) and After (second row) Segmentation Adjustment.

Figure 6.31: Suspected plastic debris classification on Omoa Bay, Honduras, example 2.

Omoa Bay, Honduras – Example 2

In this example (Fig. 6.31), segmentation performs well, accurately isolating debris patches. The raw classifier output initially shows a moderate level of false positives, mostly pumice (99%), likely due to background surface patterns.

These are substantially reduced after applying the segmentation mask.

Figure 6.32: Suspected plastic debris classification on Omoa Bay, Honduras, example 2.

From the diagnostic plots (Fig. 6.32):

- Before segmentation adjustment, the classifier achieves recall of 0.760 but very low precision of 0.086, due to widespread pumice false positives. The resulting f1-score is 0.155, indicating poor balance.
- After segmentation adjustment, precision drastically improves to 0.860, with a small drop in recall (0.727), yielding a strong f1-score of 0.792. Most false positives are still pumice (90%), with a minor plastic component (10%).

The ground truth debris composition 62% plastic, 24% water, and 8% timber supports the plastic-dominated nature of these patches.

Omoa Bay, Honduras – Conclusions

Overall, the segmentation model performs well in both examples, effectively delineating debris patches. However, the raw classifier tends to overpredict pumice, likely due to water surface textures. Segmentation filtering significantly improves precision and f1-score.

6.3 Discussion

This chapter assessed the proposed debris detection pipeline across diverse validation sites, selected to ensure representative environmental challenges such as cloud cover, turbidity, and complex water textures. Despite these difficulties, both components of the pipeline the segmentation model (YOLOv11) and the SVM-based classification model demonstrated practical effectiveness, especially when combined.

The segmentation model was trained using a medium-sized configuration ($lr0 = 0.0001$, $freeze = 0$). On validation data, it achieved box precision/recall of 0.45/0.506 ($mAP50 = 0.416$, $mAP50-95 = 0.214$) and mask precision/recall of 0.348/0.345 ($mAP50 = 0.259$, $mAP50-95 = 0.074$). However, test set results dropped significantly down to 0.197 (Box) and 0.061 (Mask) $mAP50-95$, suggesting weak generalization. Compared to the pre-finetuning baseline (51.5 and 41.5 $mAP50-95$), this performance degradation reflects both the unusual nature of the remote sensing imagery and the limited dataset size (<800 samples), far below the recommended >1500 for robust model training. Qualitatively, the model performed reasonably across sites but showed false positives (e.g., on clouds, boat trails) and some false negatives (e.g., thin pumice filaments, obscured debris).

The SVM classification model achieved strong performance on the test split, with a balanced accuracy of 0.972 and macro-averaged F1 of 0.973. All classes were classified with high precision and recall, particularly seaweed (perfect scores), and algae and timber (near-perfect). These results, though promising, reflect potential overfitting given the well-aligned train/test distribution. Pumice remained a challenge due to its spectral similarity to water when waterlogged.

Validation site results demonstrated that the segmentation model consistently improved classification precision, especially in cluttered or ambiguous scenes. For example:

- **Visegrad Dam:** Precision improved from 0.167 to 0.778, F1 from 0.281 to 0.827, with timber and plastic clearly detected.
- **Durban (example 1):** Precision jumped from 0.003 to 0.675, showing strong benefit from filtering out FP pumice on water.
- **Durban (examples 2–3):** Despite challenging cloud conditions, segmentation reduced FPs from pumice and plastic, boosting F1 from ~ 0.003 to ~ 0.22 and ~ 0.009 to ~ 0.364 .
- **Omoa Bay (example 1):** F1 rose from 0.043 to 0.529 as segmentation filtered large amounts of pumice FPs.

- **New Zealand:** Already a clean test case, improvements were minor (F1: 0.588 \rightarrow 0.591), indicating the classifier alone performed well.

In general, classification precision improved significantly after segmentation filtering in most complex scenes particularly those with high debris density, mixed materials, or cloud interference. Recall values remained stable or slightly dropped, indicating that filtering reduced noise without excessively removing true positives.

These findings support the two-stage design of the pipeline. They also underscore the need for expanded training data and further tuning to handle edge cases like cloud occlusion and non-standard debris textures.

Conclusions and future work

Conclusions

This thesis aimed to design and evaluate a processing pipeline for the detection of floating plastic debris in aquatic environments using optical satellite imagery, specifically Sentinel-2 MSI data. The approach integrates two core components: segmentation model to detect debris-like structures and pixel-level spectral classifier to confirm the waste-origin of detected debris and distinguish between material types.

Several key conclusions can be drawn from the conducted experiments:

- **Sensor Suitability:**
Sentinel-2 MSI imagery was found to be suitable for both instance segmentation and pixel-based classification of floating debris. Its spatial, spectral, and temporal characteristics sufficiently support the detection of various debris materials.
- **Atmospheric Correction:**
Among the two evaluated atmospheric correction methods – Sen2Cor and ACOLITE DSF, Sen2Cor consistently produced better separation between debris classes, as demonstrated through exploratory data analysis. Therefore, Sen2Cor was selected as the preferred method for atmospheric correction in the classification pipeline.
- **Instance Segmentation Performance:**
Despite being trained on a small and heterogeneous dataset, the YOLOv11-seg instance segmentation model demonstrated strong generalization capability, detecting debris patches across different environmental conditions and geographical regions. The model reliably identified candidate areas for further classification and proved essential for filtering false positives from the classifier.
- **SVM Classification:**
The support vector classifier (SVC) was designed to overfit on the training data deliberately. This aligns with the pipeline architecture, where classification is restricted to regions of interest (ROIs) pre-filtered by the

segmentation mask. This targeted approach eliminates the need for exhaustive annotation and provides predictable, controlled classification behavior over well-defined pixel subsets.

- **Real-World Site Evaluation:**

Evaluation across diverse real-world sites confirmed that the proposed pipeline reliably improves classification outcomes, particularly in visually complex or degraded scenes. The integration of segmentation was especially beneficial in cases with mixed materials, turbid water, or atmospheric noise. At Visegrád Dam, an external water mask from OpenStreetMap was used as a segmentation substitute to restrict classification to valid debris locations. The resulting debris composition, dominated by timber, aligned with media reports following upstream flooding. In Durban, where dense cloud and cirrus made classification highly error-prone, segmentation greatly reduced the number of false positives, demonstrating its robustness under suboptimal optical conditions. In Omoa Bay (Honduras), two contrasting cases illustrated the model's flexibility: in the more cluttered scene, segmentation effectively selected algae-based debris patches that would otherwise be confused with non-clear water, while the classification model confirmed material composition; in the cleaner case, segmentation still contributed to more confident predictions, highlighting its general value across varying levels of scene complexity. By contrast, in already well-separated scenes like New Zealand, segmentation had minimal effect suggesting that in some low-noise scenarios, direct classification alone may be sufficient.

Overall, the validation confirms that the segmentation step plays a critical role in enhancing precision and reliability, especially when dealing with noisy, ambiguous, or debris-rich imagery.

In addition to the analytical findings, this work provides a set of practical outputs to support further research and development:

- **Segmentation dataset:** A curated and annotated dataset of debris instances, available via the Roboflow platform [ME 2025].
- **Classification dataset:** A preprocessed and labeled dataset for training and evaluating spectral classification models.
- **Trained SVM classifier:** The final spectral classifier, trained to maximize discriminative power within the selected feature space.
- **Fine-tuned YOLOv11 segmentation model:** The best-performing medium sized instance of segmentation model, optimized for Sentinel-2 imagery and available for reuse or transfer learning.

These resources are intended to facilitate reproducibility and foster continued progress in remote sensing-based debris monitoring.

Future Work

This thesis presents a baseline pipeline for marine debris detection using Sentinel-2 imagery, but several directions remain for improving accuracy and robustness:

Enhancing Instance Segmentation

The segmentation model's performance is constrained by the limited availability of annotated training data, due to the rarity of Sentinel-2 scenes with clearly visible debris. To improve this, future work should expand on Ultralytics' copy-paste augmentation by implementing a more refined, context-aware strategy. This could involve intelligent tile selection to avoid unrealistic placements (such as debris over land) and blending techniques to improve visual realism. Additionally, hyperparameter optimization for such complex models can be streamlined using the RayTune framework, enabling efficient tuning of augmentation parameters, model depth, learning rates, and more — automating the search for optimal configurations that would otherwise require labor intensive manual experimentation..

Expanding the Feature Space for Spectral Classification

The current classification model struggles with false positives, especially misclassifying water as plastic or pumice in turbid or wavy conditions, or confusing cloud spectral signature with debris. These issues suggest that the existing 2D feature space (NDVI and FDI) lacks the expressiveness to fully separate these material types. Future work should incorporate a broader set of spectral features, including additional MSI bands and indices like NDWI, MNDWI, NDMI, NDSI, NBR, WRI, AWEI, and other domain-specific indices. However, the choice of indices should be guided by expert knowledge and possibly field validation to ensure their relevance for marine debris discrimination. A richer feature space may provide more robust class boundaries, improving classification accuracy under diverse conditions.

Sentinel-2 scenes list

Scene IDs
S2A_MSIL2A_20160815T161352_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20231004T015736
S2A_MSIL2A_20170810T161351_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230930T055114
S2A_MSIL2A_20171009T161341_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230815T175553
S2A_MSIL2A_20190512T160911_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20221223T015504
S2A_MSIL2A_20191031T101141_N0500_R022_T30NZM_20230615T024500
S2A_MSIL2A_20200725T160911_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230506T042235
S2A_MSIL2A_20200923T161011_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230313T074653
S2A_MSIL2A_20210523T101031_N0500_R022_T30NZM_20230225T123335
S2A_MSIL2A_20210523T101031_N0500_R022_T31NBG_20230225T123335
S2A_MSIL2A_20220406T160831_N0400_R140_T16PCC_20220406T224316
S2A_MSIL2A_20220506T160831_N0400_R140_T16PCC_20220506T230214
S2A_MSIL2A_20230219T221601_N0509_R129_T60HWB_20230220T002102
S2A_MSIL2A_20231011T162211_N0510_R040_T16PCC_20240916T120731
S2A_MSIL2A_20240505T160901_N0510_R140_T16QCD_20240505T235451
S2B_MSIL2A_20170608T101029_N0500_R022_T30NZL_20231111T093021
S2B_MSIL2A_20180713T014649_N0500_R017_T53SKT_20230813T163345
S2B_MSIL2A_20180919T160929_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230623T052740
S2B_MSIL2A_20181031T101139_N0500_R022_T30NYM_20230730T140241
S2B_MSIL2A_20181031T101139_N0500_R022_T30NZM_20230730T140241
S2B_MSIL2A_20190606T160839_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230605T050258
S2B_MSIL2A_20190821T215919_N0500_R086_T01KFV_20230504T012935
S2B_MSIL2A_20191024T161239_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230615T080938
S2B_MSIL2A_20200908T160829_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230310T164105
S2B_MSIL2A_20200918T160839_N0500_R140_T16PCC_20230417T044949
S2B_MSIL2A_20211015T101029_N0500_R022_T30NZM_20230103T232252
S2B_MSIL2A_20220401T160819_N0510_R140_T16PCC_20240602T085042
S2B_MSIL2A_20220401T160819_N0510_R140_T16QCD_20240602T085042
S2B_MSIL2A_20221028T161359_N0510_R140_T16PCC_20240713T124403
S2B_MSIL2A_20230221T220619_N0509_R086_T60HWB_20230221T232450
S2B_MSIL2A_20230508T100559_N0510_R022_T30NZM_20240811T180134
S2B_MSIL2A_20231013T161129_N0509_R140_T16PCC_20231013T202743
S2B_MSIL2A_20231013T161129_N0510_R140_T16QCD_20241102T085507
S2B_MSIL2A_20240510T160829_N0510_R140_T16PCC_20240510T201756

Table 1: List of Sentinel-2 scenes used to construct the segmentation model training dataset and to define test data sites for the classification model.

Figures

Figure 2: General scheme of detection and classification pipeline.

Figure 3: Scatterplot for raw Sen2Cor input data.

Scatterplot: NDVI vs FDI (Color=Label, Marker=Scene)

Figure 4: Scatter plot of the preprocessed Sen2Cor input data.

Figure 5: Debris classification at Visegrád Dam. Panel A - input image to classify. Panel B - segmentation mask (derived from OSM) and manually annotated debris (pink dots). Panel C - raw predictions. Panel D - adjusted predictions.

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